

A Case Study on Comparison of Typical Chinese and Western Festivals

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Abstract: *With the integration of global economy aggravating, cultural exchanges among nations become broader and more frequent, meanwhile, some typical foreign festivals and culture have diffused into China and become popular. To some extent, Chinese traditional festivals have be pounded. Therefore, this paper tries to reveal the similarities and differences between traditional Chinese and Western festival cultures by utilizing the method of comparing, inducing and deducing. First, it focuses on the introduction of some typical traditional festivals in China and western countries by comparison, then it comes to analyze the similarities and differences of traditional Chinese and western festivals. After that it explains the development trend of Chinese and western festival culture. Finally, it brings to the conclusion that comparison between Chinese and western festival culture promote a deeper understanding of western culture which is beneficial to culture exchanges among nations, which inversely helps better promote and carry forward the splendid culture of Chinese tradition.*

Keywords: Traditional Festivals, comparison, China, Western Countries

1. Introduction

There are self-evident differences in culture between Chinese and western countries, for example, language, education, festivals, and so on. No one can deny that "A holiday of a nation represents a glorious culture and concentrated customs of a nation." Festival is considered as "a carrier of culture", or an embodiment of the patterns of behavior and thinking that people learn, create and share. It is defined as a special occasion on which people give thanks for a harvest, commemorate an honored person or event, pay respect to the dead, or celebrate a culture. Through this phenomenon, it is more convenient and direct for the researcher to probe into the deeper layer of human culture from unique and specific festivals. The fundamental intention to study the traditional festival cultures between China and western countries is to carry forward the excellent traditional culture of the nation, meanwhile, to use the cream of western culture for reference to better improve the splendid culture of Chinese tradition and the modern construction of advanced culture.

This paper aims to understand the traditional value concept and profound culture psychology by comparing the differences in the traditional festivals of China and western countries, so as to dig the deep connotation of traditional festivals and recognize

objectively and systematically the nationality and features of traditional festival culture both in China and western countries. Meanwhile, it enhances culture exchanges between China and west countries, which is beneficial to promoting global economic communication and development.

2. Typical Traditional Festivals in China and Western Countries

2.1 Spring Festival vs. Christmas Day

The above two are the typical and popular festivals in their own cultural systems. The Spring Festival is the chief holiday in China while Christmas is the most important red-letter day in the western world. People attach great importance to the celebration of the two festivals.

The Spring Festival is the most distinctive Chinese folk ceremonious traditional festival, which refers to New Year's eve and the first day of a year, also called lunar year, commonly known as "Spring Festival". But in private, in the traditional sense, the Spring Festival starts from the day of the wax offering or month, 23 or 24 people, until the fifteenth, among them with New Year's eve and the first day of the first lunar month. During the Spring Festival, China's Han ethnic and minorities would held various activities to celebrate it. These activities are to worship deities, worshipping

ancestors, ChuJiuBuXin, jubilee blessing, pray for good harvest as the main content of attack. These Rich and colorful activities are with strong ethnic characteristics. It is an occasion for all family members to get together, just like Christmas in the West. All people living away from home go back to enjoy the family reunion. Many customs accompany the Spring Festival: sweep dust; "December 24, dedust and sweep house", according to the "spring and autumn annals" records, in the era of Rao sweeping the dust is one Chinese Spring Festival custom. According to the folk belief: "dust" and "Chen" homophonic, spring sweeping dust except have Chen Bu "new" meaning, the intention is to sweep all poor luck, to make bad luck go out. This custom holds the wish and pray for eradicating the old and fostering the new. When Chinese New Year approaching, every family will clean house and yard, wash all kinds of instruments, unpick and wash bedding as well as curtains, clean dust and blow grime cobweb, sewer dredging channel. Everywhere permeated with the joyful atmosphere of enthusiastically making hygiene for the Spring Festival. On New Year's eve, "shou sui" means stay up late or all night on New Year's eve, is one of the most important customs in activities, which have existed for a long time. It was first recorded in the Western Zhou Dynasty's "people": on New Year's eve, everyone does not sleep at night, stay up to the morning, called "Shou sui". Since the Han Dynasty, alternating moments from a year to the new year is commonly in the middle of the night. The first day of the New Year, people get up early and later some elites and scholars who would use the stickers for send wishes to each other, and thus developed into "greeting CARDS". To stick couplets on the Spring Festival is also the custom. Spring Festival couplets also is called a pair of antithetical phrase, peach wood charms against evil, etc. their depicting the era background, expressing good wishes, is a unique literary form in our country. Every Chinese New Year, no matter in the city or countryside, every family selects bright red Spring Festival couplets and stick them on the door, which greatly increase the festival atmosphere. Besides sticking couplets on the Spring Festival, some people stick "Fu" word on the door or wall. "Fu" word refers to the blessing, good fortune, yearning for happy life and wish for a better

future. In the folk people also like all kinds of paper cutting, paper-cut on the Windows. Spring Festival pictures, a kind of old folk art of our country, are seen common in urban and rural families, which reflects the simple customs and beliefs of the people and pins their hopes for the future. Firecrackers are widely used in festival. Setting off firecrackers can create a festive and lively atmosphere, is a kind of entertainment, which wishes bring people luckiness.

Christmas Day is a holiday held on December 25 to commemorate the birth of Jesus, the central figure of Christianity, even though the date is not known to be the actual birth date of Jesus. Although nominally a Christian holiday, Christmas is also widely celebrated by many non-Christians, and many of its popular celebratory customs have pre-Christian or secular themes and origins. Popular modern customs of the holiday include gift-giving, music, an exchange of greeting cards, church celebrations, a special meal, and the display of various decorations, including Christmas trees, lights, garlands, etc. In addition, Father Christmas (or Santa Claus) is a popular folklore figure in many countries, associated with the bringing of gifts for children. It is a time to get together with family members, relatives and friends. In the following, I will give some brief descriptions. The Christmas tree is one of the most famous and traditional Christmas celebrations. Usually people get evergreen plants such as pine trees into the house or outdoors before and after Christmas, with Christmas lights of different color on the tree and an angel or stars on the top of the tree. It is used to increase the joy of the festive atmosphere. It symbolizes forever life. On Christmas Eve, people dance and sing around Christmas tree and make merry. Christmas card is very popular in the United States and Europe, which is one of the ways to maintain relationships with distant relatives and friends. You can use them to send your wishes to them. People use Christmas stockings to load gifts, which are children's favorite things, on Christmas Eve they would hang their socks in the bed and receive gifts the next morning. During the holidays, people come to the church to hold a grand ritual, but also a colorful celebration. On December 24 evening, the whole family usually get together to hold a Christmas dinner.

The food is of variety, rich and colorful. The main dish is the turkey. In the eyes of western, it is not called Christmas without turkey.

Christmas Day is celebrated as a major festival and public holiday in most countries of the world, even in many whose populations are not Christian majorities. In some non-Christian countries or areas such as Hong Kong, former colonial rules are introduced to the celebration, Christian minorities or foreign cultural influences have led populations to observe the holiday. Around the world, Christmas celebrations vary greatly in form, reflecting different cultural and national traditions. Countries such as Japan and Korea, where Christmas is popular despite there are only a small number of Christians, have adopted many of the secular aspects of Christmas, such as gift-giving, decorations and Christmas trees.

2.2 Other Main Festivals of Western Countries and China

The Chinese Qingming festival is rich and interesting. Its traditional customs are sweeping the tomb and give honor to ancestors. It also pays attention to ban on fire. There are some custom sports such as outgoing, playing on the swing, playing the polo, and so on. Dragon boat racing is the main custom of the Dragon Boat Festival. The festival is said to originate from the legend that Qu Yuan committed suicide and jump into Yuluo River, and the Chu people raced their boat to save him. Eating dumplings is another custom for the festival. In addition, during the festival, people will hang moxa calamus in front of the door. And wear perfume bag which is made up with a kind of leaves. It was believed that it is able to ward evil and avoid illness. Besides the Spring Festival, only the Mid-Autumn Festival is the occasion for family to get together. It is also known as the Moon Festival. is a popular harvest festival celebrated by people in the Chinese influenced world, dating back over 3,000 years to moon worship in China's Shang Dynasty. It is also celebrated by the Vietnamese, Koreans, and Japanese in different forms. At the night with full moon hanging in the sky, the family sat around the table, tasting delicious food and enjoying the bright

and round moon. In addition, eating moon cakes is also the tradition. The round moon cakes symbol reunion of the family. The Mid-Autumn Festival is held on the 15th day of the eighth month in the Chinese calendar, which is usually around late September or early October on the Gregorian calendar. In the west, on the Thanksgiving Day, people go to do thanksgiving prayer in the church. People always strive to return home from far apart, staying together with family members and have delicious turkey as well as talking about the past. It is worth mentioning, thanksgiving day food is very of tradition, and the turkey is the main traditional course. There are make-up parades, drama performances and sports competitions in urban and rural towns. Thanksgiving or Thanksgiving Day is a harvest festival celebrated primarily in the United States and Canada. Traditionally, Thanksgiving is associated with giving thanks to God for the harvest and expressing gratitude. While historically religious in origin, Thanksgiving is now primarily identified as a secular holiday. Halloween, as one of the most important festival in the west, it holds attention from people. On that day, in front of every door hangs a pumpkin lamp. Every one dresses oddly. The two customs are said to ward off bad luck. Actually, people in developed countries are no longer superstitious. They do these things for joy. Meanwhile, people also hold a grand masked ball. They can be arbitrary to beg food from their neighbors, and won't get punished or condemned.

3. Common Ground of Traditional Chinese and Western Festivals

Through the introduction on the typical festivals of the two cultural systems in pairs, this paper will make specific comparison on them in the following.

3.1 Similarities in Perspective of the Functions of the Festivals

It can be said that significance of all the traditional festivals and their celebrations won't come into being, even if there is, it would quickly be eliminated. Therefore, all Chinese and western traditional festivals passed down generation by generation are purposeful and meaningful with clear functions and stable value.

These traditional festivals act as the media of culture passing the culture to next generations. The similar functions between the festivals of the two cultural systems can be listed as below.

3.1.1 The Yearning and Pursuit for A Happy and Bliss Life

In the traditional holiday ceremonies, the Chinese and western festivals show rich and colorful performances to express the joy of people's heart. As to Chinese people, traditional festivals means leisure, joy, warmness and happiness. All the feelings last in one's heart who experiences the dilution of the traditional festivals. Generally speaking, setting off firecrackers during Spring Festival and the yangko dance, the dragon dance in Lantern Festival, flying a kite in Tomb-sweeping Day, the dragon boat racing in Dragon Boat Day and climbing during the Chung Yeung Festival, all the celebrations shows joy and happiness for life. Besides, the festival food like 'Happy group' and so on also show people's joyful feeling. And this feeling is exactly comes from people's endless love to life. In western countries, traditional festivals also show people's exact feeling of love and pursue for life. Spring Festival, is a festival of reunion and happy. People try to get home before the New Year's Eve to get together with their families. This is also true of western Christmas Day. Westerners also go back home to stay together with family members. They pay much attention to the whole family party, sitting under the tree, singing Christmas carols and praying to happiness. Other western festivals like Fiesta de San Fermin in Span, American Hot pepper Festival in Hatch are also have that function.

3.1.2 The Continuity of the Traditional Virtue and the Respect to the Dead People.

The filial piety culture have a long history. "Treat other's elder as mine, love other's children as mine" the conception of respecting the old and loving the young is reflected in the traditional festival culture which have a long history. For instance, ancestor worship, paying New Year's visits to the elder and giving pocket money to children etc, all show care for the old and the

young. There are no other festivals like the Double Ninth Festival shows that traditional virtue. The same is the western traditional festivals that show the traditional virtue. The special festivals like Mother's Day, Father's Day, Baby's day and so on is for expressing respect and filial piety for elder and expressing love to children. Maternal Grand Mother and Father of the USA, all of the old, not only Grand mother and father will receive the respect and love from offspring, relatives and friends.

3.1.3 The Desire for Eternal Love

Love is a permanent topic for human beings. For example, Chinese Double-Seventh Day, known as Magpie Festival and western Valentine's Day, which show people's piety for love. traditionally on this day, young girls display their domestic arts, especially melon carving, and make wishes for a good husband on the seventh day of July on the Chinese lunar calendar. The festival is based on the story of the cowherd and the weaver girl whose true love moved magpies. West Saint Valentine's Day (commonly shortened to Valentine's Day) is an annual commemoration held on February 14 for intimate companions to celebrate love and affection, which fully shows the desire for eternal love.

3.1.4 The Worship of Historical Heroes.

Although according to Marxist viewpoint, history is the masses to create. People also respect and worship these who do great things in history. During Chinese traditional festivals, there are not only festivals custom for ancestor worship, but also for admiration of historical heroes. Although people do worship and prayer for the heroes, these are one way of admiration such as Chinese Cold Food Festival which was said to pay admiration to Jie Zitui, a historical hero who didn't take credit working for the country and choose to retreat. And Dragon Boat Day is said to admire great poet Qu Yuan who concerned about his country and his people. Other minority's festival like Zhuang's festival March Street is for Liu Sanjie. Western festivals see admiration for historical heroes a lot. Such as Christmas Day, it is to commemorate the Christ Jesus ,

Columbus's Day for Columbus San Marino Day for San Maruno and so on.

In conclusion, no matter Chinese traditional festivals or western ones, the festive customs function as the media to transmit culture. Meanwhile, the two festival system in general transmit the same culture concept, only the specific way is different and have their own characteristics.

3.2 Similarities in Perspective of the Origins of the Festivals

It is often said that every tree has its root and each river has its source. Chinese and western festivals have their roots. Of course, due to historical, cultural and natural background are inconsistent, so their origins are distinct. However, from the perspective of the origin of nature, both have many similarities.

3.2.1 Religious Roots

Religion, as a very old culture phenomenon, inevitably have much relationship with holiday. Although China is not a religious country, folk scholars pointed out that among the nationality festivals in our country, many originated from religious roots.

Chinese traditional festival is formed between the Xia dynasty and Zhou dynasty. After the Zhou dynasty, they were improved. During this time, local Chinese primitive religious, native Taoism, Buddhism and Islam have varying effects in then. The worship of gods has become a important part of festival celebration. Many festivals like the Lantern Festival, Chinese Ghost Festival and so on has proved that. As the traditional festivals in China, western festival culture is also deeply influenced by religious. Since the Christian civilization was disseminated in the European, the Christian have influenced almost all of the large festivals in Europe.

3.2.2 Celebration for Harvest

Ancient China has been a feudal self-sufficient agricultural society which holds natural economy.

Thus the traditional festival has a strong agricultural color. In the process of agricultural civilization, people sum up the elements, the twenty-four solar terms and formed the main festivals. Dating back to ancient china, the Spring Festival, Tomb-sweeping Festival were deemed as important farming festivals. Some of them were celebrated for the harvest such as the Mid-autumn Day. People celebrate the good harvest through festivals, and pray for the coming year by worship. Also in the west, many festivals come from harvest activities such as Thanksgiving Day and Tomato Day in Czech. They both celebrate for customs, although the customs may differ from each other.

3.3 The Common Characteristics of Festival Culture

Seen from the festival culture itself, Chinese and western traditional festivals have periodicity, integrity and variability.

3.3.1 The Periodicity of Festival

It could be said that periodicity is the first characteristics of traditional festivals. Chinese and western festivals are setted in a certain time. And all the festivals are celebrated every year---circle to circle. Chinese traditional festival periodicity is very obvious. All the festivals fall on the four seasons periodically. Periodicity of western holidays is a year in the Gregorian calendar. Chinese and western traditional festivals are held periodically, which is conducive to strengthen national tradition and culture.

3.3.2 The Integrity in Festival

Integrity in festival means that traditional festivals, as the important carrier of national culture, have characteristics of strong inclusion and cover. As to the integrity in festival, it can be said that Chinese and western traditional culture is a comprehensive cultural phenomenon. It consists of festive language, tools, food, rules of etiquette and feelings and so on, which can be classified into material, culture and behavior culture. Chinese and west main traditional festivals have the integrity, such as Chinese Spring Festival,

Dragon Boat Day, Mid-autumn Day and western Christmas Day, Easter, Halloween, etc. All the main festivals are integrity of culture factors.

3.3.3 Variability in Festival

Variability is one of the main characteristics of culture. Human society is changing and developing. Festival culture which is closely linked with the society is keeping ahead with the times. With the continuous development of culture, the traditional festival culture also presents the same trend. For instance, in Chinese traditional festivals New Year, traditional customs like setting off firecrackers, sticking couplets have changed from for expelling evil and ghost to auspiciousness and happiness. In western traditional festivals, variability is one of the main characteristics of culture, such as Halloween, once is the holiday to pay honor to the spirit of the dead, now to some extent, have changed into the time for people especially the young to have fun.

4. Differences of Traditional Chinese and Western Festivals

4.1 The Differences of the Cultural Background.

Although Chinese and western festival culture have in common and similarities, or even are the same in some aspects, there are different points between the two festive customs. Apart from different background for traditional festival culture, the traditional Chinese festival cultures are based on farming culture, while the traditional western festival cultures take the background of Christianity.

4.1.1 Agriculture Cultural Background for Chinese Festivals

China is an ancient Orient civilized country, whose long history and tradition provided for the traditional festivals to grow in fertile soil, and Chinese culture is deeply rooted in agriculture. Therefore, the agricultural activities add more local color to festivals. Spring Festival and some agricultural activities are closely related to planting, harvest and so on. As the most

important holiday in China, Spring Festival's origins can be dated back to thousands of years evolving great many colorful legends and traditions.

As traditional Chinese festival cultures are under the background of farming culture, people's living pattern affects the way and content of social life. The main traditional festival of china is converted by the lunar calendar, with the full color of agriculture. The activities of Chinese traditional festival are all produced according to the lunar calendar. Chinese people want to use some celebrations activities in slack season to express their best wishes for favorable climatic weathers. Because of the lower productive power in the remote geologic time, human could not recognize and understand scientifically the rules and phenomenon of nature. Therefore, they have the worship about the god, the earth, the ancestor at the different degree. Gradually, they offer sacrifices to gods or ancestors, which has close relations with the agriculture, such as pray for a good harvest, ancestor worship. Meanwhile, because Chinese people are in the self-sufficiency agriculture society and natural economy of feudal system, which influences the traditional festival with the color of agriculture. Some festivals documents like Magpie Festival show that cowboy doing farming work, while the girl-weaver engaged in spinning and weaving. It is self-sufficient small family economical model which dyes strong agricultural color.

4.1.2 Christian Cultural Background for Western Countries Traditional Festivals

On the contrary, the origin of western traditional festivals is full of religion color. Since the Europe continent was infected by the Christian civilization, nearly all important traditional festival has some relation with religion. In the western countries, because of the foundation and spreading of the Christian and the agriculture economy has been replaced by the commodity economy of industrial society. Gradually, the festivals derived by variable religion consciousness replaced the celebration customs which piously worship the land and pray for harvest. Although the western countries originated

from the stock raising, the agriculture did not become the foundation for the country. Therefore people focus on the climate less than that in China; on the contrary they mostly focus on Christianity. Moreover, most western countries always formed a religion, a nation and then respectively formed their own country. That makes the traditional festivals have the religion colors in the origin period and then strengthen in the process of development.

In western countries, as a social and cultural center, religion controls westerners' spirit for their beliefs on god or religion. It is not exaggerate to say, religion exists in all walks of life. What's more, the festival is closely related with the Christian Christmas, Easter, except with religion.

Western culture is influenced by the traditional Christian festivals with strong religious origins, such as Valentine's day (memorial named Watts of Christian martyrs (Easter), commemorates the resurrection, Halloween (all saints), church memorial commemorates the birth of Jesus (Christmas), the origin of these festivals are closely related to religion.

4.2 From the Custom Differences

4.2.1 The Different Custom in Food

Every traditional festival has its own special way to celebrate. They also have different contents of festival culture. Chinese and western festivals differ in many ways . Traditional Chinese festival cultures are characterized by food and wine. While traditional western festival cultures are characterized by entertainment.

The topic of Chinese traditional festival custom is mainly about the diet. Chinese people notice more about the diet. Any Chinese traditional festival, whether is the Spring Festival, the Tomb-sweeping Day or Dragon Boat Festival, diet custom is an important part of the festival culture. For instance, many sweet food and dumpling in Spring Festival, moon cakes in Mid-autumn Day and traditional Chinese rice-pudding in Dragon Boat Day. The rich

diet culture have been a indispensable part of traditional festive celebration, which not only meet people's physical needs, but also activate the atmosphere of traditional festivals. The features of Chinese diet culture became the metaphor symbol system, which not only regards to the civilization achievements, but also a kind of national psychology with the high believes and forbidden. The kind of metaphor and symbol concentrated in the diet of festival custom. It is the result of the mind concept and value orientation. Chinese people aim to pursue the health and longevity of life, and the food is the basic way to achieve the goals. In addition, Chinese philosophy emphasis on the elemental harmony, which means human, should be compatible with the nature.

While western holidays also have series of festive food, such as Christmas roasted goose, the resurrection eggs in Easter, turkey in Thanksgiving, pumpkin bread. etc, much more people are looking forward the pursuit of mental life joy, or sacredness of the religion. Christmas carols, carnival event for relax, delicate and charming rose, Bizarre ghost masks, the dance or ceremonies, all at least looks more attend the emotional needs. The western people treat the pursuit way of life as the attention to be healthy and happy. They think that, except the necessary food, it is more important to realize the goals by the religion and entertainment activities.

4.2.2 The Differences in the Time and Way of Celebration.

Different festivals have different time. Even the Chinese traditional festivals in the same system are celebrated in the different time. Such as the Spring Festival is the first day of a year in lunar calendar, while the Latten Day and other traditional festivals are celebrated in succession at different time. Let alone the two different festival systems in different customs. For instance, Christmas Day is celebrated on December 25th, which differs from other festivals. As the way to celebration, Chinese and west traditional festivals they all have their own customs and culture characteristic. Most of the Chinese traditional festivals are held in the range of family and different festivals and different

festivals have special festive diet with its unique cultural implication. The western traditional festivals focus more on individuals to participating in the community interaction, with a survival from the nomadic culture and business civilization. The western holidays are more celebrated in community activities that it is by individual participation that to achieve the goal of social communication. This reflects the extroversion of western culture and decrease the family color in the festivals.

4.3 Value Differences between China and Western Countries

The next difference in the perspective of inner meaning is that they have different value orientation. Traditional Chinese festival cultures value collectivism. Chinese festivals attach far more importance to group activity and the passing down of ethics and virtues. But traditional western festival cultures value individualism, which put great emphasis on the expression of personal needs and individual psychological emotions and feelings.

4.3.1 Collective Cultural Value in Chinese Traditional Festival

Chinese traditional festivals pay more attention to family collective activities. Most of Chinese traditional festivals, mainly show a strong clan and family values and the concept of social groups. Each festival is centered around the family and family activities, such as New Year, the lantern Festival, Mid-autumn festival, reflect the family union theme. "reunion dinner", "moon cakes", "regiment round dumplings" and their appearance, as well as some poetry, which define the festival concept from different aspects. In China, people seek for health, union, and harmony. Food is a main factor mean that we become better and better year by year. People eat moon cakes in Middle-autumn Day and Laba porridge in Laba festival. In the Chinese Moon festival, people use the moon cake to enact togetherness, harmoniousness traditional moon-cake is round, which symbolizes the family circle, and its sweet flavor echoes the sweetness of filial ties, by cutting and sharing moon-cake, the family circle is

repeated and the tie of blood are strengthened. Family reunification for Spring Festival, the New Year's eve is the last year of December in lunar year, that night all members in a family will get together to enjoy the "family union dinner" no matter how it is far from home, even how hard it is. Form the second day of first lunar year. People bring altogether with each other, and take the gifts to visit their relatives and friends. Visiting each other is a good way to strengthen the relationship with each other.

4.3.2 Individual Culture value in Western Traditional Festival

Western culture pursues individualism, self-centered, and it emphasize on personality, competition, and dignity. Westerners believed that the individual is the basis of the society, each person's life pattern and quality depend on personal abilities. The individual is higher than society. Westerners focus on "human nature" "nature" "the pursuit of liberalism" and keen on exploring individual value. In essence, it is a kind of individualism. Analysis is as follow:

For westerners, they celebrate the festivals differently by way of going out and having fun. to There are colorful and exciting activities to celebrate the independence day, including picnics, playing fireworks and parades. Westerners take the realization of individual value as the most important one, and they like to express their own feelings freely. For example, saint valentine day is a good opportunity for westerners to express their romantic love. On the contrary, Chinese people are more confined to the old tradition.

Similarly, the western "Ghost Festival" is the Halloween. children dress up in costumes at night on Halloween and play pumpkin lanterns-pumpkins are a traditional way of the celebration. All people have party and play games. On that day, people can do everything or make jokes or troubles as they like and never mind other's resentment and feeling, because everyone does as well. All people are happy and enjoy themselves in harmony with nature, so everyone is an individual that can do everything they want during the

festival such as the Mid-autumn Day, the Spring Festival and so on. The core idea of Chinese traditional festivals emphasize the “reunion” such as the Mid-autumn Day, the Spring Festival and so on. The “reunion” is located in a small scope, with certain exclusivity.

5. The Future trends of Chinese and Western Traditional Festivals

5.1 The Integration of Traditional Festival Culture between China and Western Countries.

Human society has gradually moved to the information age, economic and cultural exchanges and infiltration frequently take place between regions and nations. In the multicultural exchange and penetration, British civilization showed great output advantage. Some people argued that this kind of culture with strong stance support economic hegemony in the British powers, i.e, prop up the cultural hegemony, resulting in the culture of the invasion and permeability. Nowadays, globalization greatly promotes the Chinese and western cultural exchange, some of the western festivals and customs such as Christmas, Valentine's Day, April Fool's Day Mother's Day, etc have been introduced into China. By contrast, some of the Chinese traditional festivals, such as Tomb-sweeping Day, Dragon Boat Festival, the Mid-autumn Day, Chung Yeung Festival and so on, due to the prevalence of western festivals, to a certain extent, are blown by the impact. For instance, Chinese people especially the young pay more attention to western festivals. They send rose and chocolate to their boyfriends or girlfriends to celebrate the western Valentine's Day but ignore the Chinese one about love, they even don't really know the time of that Chinese traditional festival. People even pay less attention to Dragon Boat Festival which results in Republic of Korea claimed the traditional Chinese festival is created by Korean people and requires the application to their own culture.

To some extent, the Chinese traditional festivals have been changed into diet section. In the memories of Chinese people, eating seems to be the real part of

festival. Eating dumplings for Spring Festival, moon cake for Mid-autumn Day, zongzi in Dragon Boat Day. It seems that just eating these food in the certain festivals means have the festive celebration. But if you don't stay up all the night during the Spring festival, you don't enjoy the colorful lanterns in Yuan Xiao festival and without the appreciation of the beautiful moon in the Mid-autumn Day, what is the differences between the traditional festivals and other days? What is to be the carrier of the corresponding folk culture?

The festival, as a carrier of culture, ever and now proceeds to play the key role of carrying forward the culture. Traditional Chinese festivals have great value in traditional culture which reflects noble quality of Chinese people in reforming nature and society, and should be inherited by next generations. Paying more attention to the traditional Chinese festivals is a good way to inherit the folk culture, we must do both to maintain the national character, and reflects the trends. In other words, while maintaining the traditional culture gene, we should attach importance to keeping pace with the times.

5.2 Western Festivals' Impact on Chinese Traditional Festivals

We Chinese people have the responsibility to maintain Chinese traditional festivals which represents part of Chinese culture. Chinese traditional festivals always have their own national characteristic such as the lion dancing, rowing barge and other activities during the Spring Festival. From rehearsal show to performance, they embody the Chinese nation harmony and family harmony.

The traditional culture of China needs to pass down through education. If we today teach our generation science and technology only focusing on economy development, then what kind of patriotic spirit and national emotion will talents own? Also, if we do not educate our offsprings how to distinguish right from wrong, how can they take in the advantage of the west culture excessive globalization along with its economic globalization. Of course, by school education only to inherit traditional culture and absorb

the nutrition of the western culture is not enough. More is needed and relied on the joint efforts of family and even the whole society.

5.3 Comments on The Studies

There is a contrast that the western festivals we accepted are more than that we transmit. Differences between Chinese and western traditional festivals are complementary to the world culture, which adds to the richness and color of world culture exchange. Currently, we should confess the recognition of our traditional festival, and then exert ourselves to expand our traditional festival culture to the world.

First, we should fully recognize that the world needs the cultural diversity of traditional festivals. China has the very rich traditional festivals resources. In order to form a diversity structure of the world cultural, in view of the report, we should have a kind of consensus that China should strive to expand the rich cultural elements of traditional festivals into Western countries in today's economic globalization, so as to spread the brilliant culture of Chinese nation and let the western countries share our spiritual civilizations. Then we should make great efforts to spread the traditional festivals cultural. That is, we should maintain a good mentality to spread the traditional festival cultural as a good main body and keep up with the development of communication by translation work.

6. Conclusion

Chinese and Western culture have their own different characteristics, especially ethnic characteristics. The old saying "Discard the dross and select the essence" is the correct method to treat the western culture. Through the above analysis and comparison we can have a conclusion that there are some differences in the traditional festival culture between Chinese and Western countries, such as the origin, the way to celebrate, custom, potential value and so on. In the exchanges of the two cultures, China, as a great civilization, has a colorful traditional culture. However, in the current background of the globalization, only by constantly enhancing the overall national strength,

including the improvement of culture competitive power and keep the vitality of traditional festivals, we can integrate into the international community, and thus it is invincible.

The comparative study of traditional festival culture between China and western countries holds great significance in protection of national characteristics and carrying forward the national spirit both in theory and practice, but the academic concern for the subject is still not enough relative for its significances. The current study always stresses on some aspects, without the comprehensive and systematical analysis or the deeper research. Therefore, the report requires more scholars to concern about this area through exploration so as to promote culture development.

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Acknowledgements

The research is financed by fund program¹: 2011 Nanchang Normal University Program, Title: Research on Teaching Intensive reading by Comparison of English and Chinese Language No. 11JY03

fund program²: 2015 Nanchang Normal University

English Education Research Creative Group Program
No. NSTD20143003

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Lei Xuelian received the bachelor's degree in English language from Nanchang University of China in 2003, and postgraduate degree in English Curriculum and teaching theory from Hangzhou Normal university of China in 2009. From 2009 to now, she have been teaching languages in English department of Nanchang Normal University, Jiangxi province, China.